

RESEARCH DIGEST

The value of low-and negative-carbon fuels in the transition to net-zero emission economies: Lifecycle greenhouse gas emissions and cost assessments across multiple fuel types

Fangwei Cheng, Hongxi Luo, Jesse D. Jenkins, and Eric D. Larson
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In recent macro-energy systems modeling studies of net-zero emissions pathways for the United States and elsewhere, hydrogen, synthetic liquid and gaseous fuels made via carbon neutral or carbon negative processes play critical roles as energy carriers in net-zero greenhouse gas emissions economies. In this study, we develop lifecycle greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and cost assessments to provide insights into the environmental and economic cost and value of hydrogen (H₂), synthetic natural gas (SNG), and Fischer-Tropsch liquid (FTL) fuels made from 1) biomass, coupled with CCS, 2) natural gas, with CCS, and 3) renewably-generated electricity. We find that H₂ production pathways are less costly to decarbonize than FTL and SNG pathways that use the same input feedstock and also provide the largest reductions in lifecycle GHG emissions per unit of delivered fuel. Sensitivity analyses on the levelized costs of carbon mitigation (LCCM) indicate that capital costs and capacity factors are influential for most of the pathways. Costs for processes that use natural gas as feedstock are more sensitive to changes in input feedstock intensity than other processes. Finally, we find that fuel production pathways starting from biomass and including CCS have the highest carbon mitigation potentials among all feedstock pathways. They also have the lowest production costs beyond certain threshold carbon emission price levels. Our findings help explain the critical role that biomass-based hydrogen production with CCS plays in macro-energy system models of the U.S. transition to net-zero emissions.

Low- and negative-carbon emissions fuels such as hydrogen, Fischer-Tropsch liquid (FTL) fuels, and synthetic natural gas (SNG) could play critical roles in transition to net zero carbon-emission economies. For example, H₂ can replace fossil fuels in chemicals production, be blended into pipeline gas to help decarbonize the natural gas sector and decarbonize sectors that are difficult to electrify such as long-distance heavy-duty trucks and heavy industry (e.g., steel production). Similarly, synthetic liquid fuels can substitute for fossil-derived liquid fuels in difficult-to-electrify transportation applications, such as heavy-duty trucks, trains, and planes. Likewise, clean SNG can be used to help decarbonize industries where electrical heating is not available and natural gas power plants that are not equipped with CO₂ capture. These fuels can be produced from a variety of feedstocks via multiple fuel conversion pathways. To date, most of the published techno-economic assessments of clean H₂, FTL, and SNG production pathways focus on evaluating different pathways for a single energy carrier, making cross-fuel comparisons difficult.

Princeton University's Zero-carbon Energy systems Research and Optimization Laboratory conducts research to improve decision-making and accelerate rapid, affordable, and effective transitions to net-zero carbon energy systems. The ZERO Lab improves and applies optimization-based modeling tools and methods to understand complex macro-scale energy systems and uses these tools to evaluate and optimize emerging low-carbon energy technologies and generate decision-relevant insights to guide national and sub-national jurisdictions in transitioning to net-zero emissions energy systems. Prof. Jesse D. Jenkins is the Principal Investigator. For more, see <https://mae.princeton.edu/people/faculty/jenkins>

Energy Systems Analysis Group focuses on identifying technologies and technology strategies and policies that could facilitate solutions for the long term of major energy-related societal problems—including global climate change, urban air pollution, energy-import dependence, the risk of nuclear weapons proliferation, and poverty in developing countries. Dr. Eric Larson and Dr. Chris Greig are the Principal Investigator. For more, see <https://acee.princeton.edu/research/energy-systems-analysis-group>

In the work presented here, we seek to address these literature gaps by developing lifecycle GHG emissions and cost assessments across different low-carbon/carbon-negative H₂, FTL, and SNG production pathways. This enables more rigorous and consistent assessment of the relative value of the different fuels in a greenhouse-gas emissions constrained world. Our analyses provide estimates of life cycle GHG emissions and levelized costs of fuel (LCOF) as a function of carbon emissions price for each pathway, along with levelized costs of carbon mitigation (LCCM), i.e., the carbon emissions price at which the low- or negative-carbon fuel option would have the same cost as the corresponding conventional, fossil-derived benchmark fuel pathway. We also carry out parametric sensitivity analyses to assess the impact of performance and cost sensitivity on our findings.

Methods

We evaluated 16 routes for H₂, FTL, and SNG production (Table 1). We have assessed a conventional route (i.e., steam methane reforming) plus five low- or negative-carbon emissions hydrogen production routes: two based on natural gas reforming with carbon capture and storage (CCS), biomass-gasification routes with and without CCS, and electrolysis. We have also conducted assessments that integrate each of these hydrogen production routes with reverse water gas shift (RWGS) Fischer-Tropsch synthesis (FTS) and methanation technologies to assess ten additional fuel production routes.

Table 1. Hydrogen (H₂), Fischer-Tropsch liquids (FTL), and synthetic natural gas (SNG) production pathways

Fuel	Pathway	Label	Technology	Energy Input ^a
H ₂	P1	SMR	Steam methane reforming	NG
	P2	SMR-CCS	Steam methane reforming w/CCS	NG
	P3	ATR-CCS	Autothermal reforming w/CCS	NG
	P4	Electrolysis	Electrolysis	Elec
	P5	BG-H2	Gasification + water-gas-shift	Bio
	P6	BGCCS-H2	Gasification + water-gas-shift w/CCS	Bio
FTL	P7	SMR-FTL	SMR-CCS + RWGS-FTS	NG
	P8	ATR-FTL	ATR-CCS + RWGS-FTS	NG
	P9	Elec-FTL	Electrolysis + RWGS-FTS	Elec
	P10	BG-FTL	BG-H2 + RWGS-FTS	Bio
	P11	BGCCS-FTL	BGCCS-H2 + RWGS-FTS	Bio
SNG	P12	SMR-SNG	SMR-CCS + Methanation	NG
	P13	ATR-SNG	ATR-CCS + Methanation	NG
	P14	Elec-SNG	Electrolysis + Methanation	Elec
	P15	BG-SNG	BG-H2 + Methanation	Bio
	P16	BGCCS-SNG	BGCCS-H2 + Methanation	Bio

(a) NG = natural gas, Bio = biomass, Elec = Electricity

We use life cycle assessment and tech-economic assessment to determine the cradle-to-gate GHG emissions (t CO₂e/GJ, Figure 1) and levelized cost of fuel (\$/GJ) of all the technological routes. In addition, we compute levelized costs of carbon mitigation (LCCM) for low- or negative-carbon emissions pathways (P2-P16). The LCCM (eqn 1) corresponds to the incremental economic cost incurred for a process divided by the environmental gain associated with the process relative to the corresponding benchmark process. The benchmark process for hydrogen, FTL, and SNG is SMR (P1), fossil-derived jet fuel, and fossil-derived natural gas, respectively. The LCCM order reflects the economic feasibility of low- and negative- carbon emissions fuels against their fossil benchmark in the context of carbon prices.

$$LCCM_p = \frac{(LCOF_p - LCOF_{benchmark})[\$ \text{ per GJ energy}]}{(GHG_{benchmark} - GHG_p)[t \text{ CO}_2\text{e per GJ energy}]} \quad (1)$$

Figure 1. The carbon system boundaries (dashed lines) of evaluated pathways. Green boundaries represent H₂ production routes (P1-P6); orange boundaries represent FTL/SNG production routes (P7-P16). All arrows represent carbon flows (CO₂ equivalents). Arrows crossing a dashed line represent emissions to or from the atmosphere. “From atmosphere” is CO₂ that originates in the atmosphere and is removed via direct air capture or is produced from photosynthesized CO₂, i.e., biomass.

Findings

Our results support the idea that H₂ has a critical role to play in transitions to decarbonized fuel systems. We find that LCOFs for decarbonized H₂ are significantly lower than for low-carbon liquid fuel or synthetic natural gas for the same feedstock inputs (Figure 2). This pattern is also reflected in levelized cost of carbon mitigation (LCCM) values (Figure 3), with H₂ made from natural gas with CO₂ capture and storage offering the lowest LCCM (about 60 \$/tCO₂e, in a U.S. context). This suggests that decarbonized H₂ from natural gas could enter the fuels sector earlier than decarbonized liquids or synthetic natural gas. As carbon mitigation ambitions grow, and the effective price of GHG emissions grows, H₂ made from biomass with CO₂ capture and storage (BGCCS-H₂) becomes the more attractive H₂ option on a LCOF basis, and the highly-negative emissions for this pathway results in a declining LCOF as the carbon emissions price increases (Figure 4). Meanwhile, the LCOF for other decarbonized H₂ pathways increase with GHG emissions price, albeit more slowly than the LCOF for the benchmark pathway, and so these options eventually compete favorably with the benchmark when emission prices are high enough.

In the case of decarbonized FTL and SNG, BGCCS pathways are the most competitive on a LCOF basis above certain threshold carbon price levels. The breakeven carbon price is 190 \$/t for BGCCS-FTL and 250 \$/t CO₂ for BGCCS-SNG. The LCOF for pathways to decarbonized FTL and SNG using natural gas, electricity, and biomass without CCS have much higher breakeven carbon prices (> 400 \$/t). This suggests that those pathways, at least in the U.S. context, are likely to be deployed only where the more-competitive biomass coupled with CCS option is not available. Furthermore, if sufficient negative emissions are available at a marginal cost below these very high breakeven prices, it may never make economic sense to pursue these decarbonization pathways. Additionally, in the case of SNG, another competitor is decarbonized H₂, which has the potential to be used in many applications where natural gas is used today.

Our sensitivity analysis in LCCM shows that the economic competitiveness of many pathways is largely influenced by capital costs and capacity factors (Figure 5). Feedstock costs are also influential for certain types of technology (e.g., electricity price for electrolysis, carbon neutral CO₂ for fuel synthesis), but not sensitive

if the benchmark technology and evaluated technology used the same type of feedstocks (e.g., SMR/ATR-CCS for H₂ production). **When natural gas is used as feedstock, input feedstock intensity (IFI) is the most important parameter as it affects both feedstock costs and GHG emissions** (Figure 6). One particularly interesting finding is that for biomass pathways with CCS, it may be more favorable economically to sacrifice some energy conversion efficiency to reduce capital-intensity, since lower fuel conversion efficiency is compensated by greater negative CO₂ emissions, which may outweigh the reduction in fuel production depending on the relative value of fuel and negative emissions.

Figure 2. LCOF without carbon price (top panel) and life cycle GHG emissions with GWP₁₀₀ and GWP₂₀ (bottom panel) for H₂, FTL, and SNG production pathways.

Figure 3. LCCM of H₂, FTL, and SNG pathways with biomass (blue), clean electricity (yellow), and natural gas (blue) as feedstocks; GWP₁₀₀ (dashed) and GWP₂₀ (dotted) are used to reflect long-term and short-term climate impacts.

Figure 4. LCOF for H₂, FTL, and SNG production pathways as a function of carbon price. The lifecycle GHG emissions of each pathway is based on GWP₁₀₀. Dashed lines represent the benchmark pathways for H₂, FTL, and SNG.

Figure 5. Variation in LCCM for 100-year time horizon relative to values in Figure 3: H₂ pathways (left panel); FTL pathways (middle panel); SNG pathways (right panel). Each parameter variation is +10% (green) and -10% (red). The resulting changes are proportional to the magnitudes of input changes because results are linear with changes in each of the examined parameters. For sensitivity parameters without any results indicated, mean the impacts were zero or negligible. The x-axis units are percent of the LCCM value in Figure 3 for the corresponding pathway.

Figure 6. Changes of LCCM (GWP₁₀₀) when changing the input feedstock intensity (IFI) by $\pm 10\%$. IFI represents the feedstock inputs divided by product outputs on energy basis (GJ_{in}/GJ_{out}). Positive (negative) values are increases (decreases) compared to the baseline LCCM (i.e., values shown in Figure 3). The resulting changes are proportional to the magnitudes of input changes because results are linear with changes in each of the examined parameters. For the FTL and SNG pathways, only the IFI associated with the H₂ production portion of the process is modified.

About the authors

Fangwei Cheng is an associate research scholar in the Andlinger Center for Energy and the Environment at Princeton University. [@fangwei_cheng](#)

Hongxi Luo is postdoctoral research associate in the Andlinger Center for Energy and the Environment at Princeton University.

Eric D. Larson is a senior research engineer in the Andlinger Center for Energy and the Environment at Princeton University.

Jesse D. Jenkins is an assistant professor at Princeton University with joint appointments in the Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering and Andlinger Center for Energy and the Environment. [@jessejenkins](#)

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